

THE MECHANISM OF ENHANCED MOISTURE
ABSORPTION AND DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN COMPOSITES
EXPOSED TO THERMAL SPIKES

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ABSTRACT

Dry and moisture conditioned crossply laminates, fabricated from Narmco Rigidite 5245C prepreg, have been subjected to a carefully selected range of thermal spiking temperatures. A critical temperature of 175°C has been identified above which damage in the form of transverse cracks results. This is accompanied by a weight loss between cycles. Below 175°C, thermal spiking leads to an enhanced moisture uptake. The enhancement of the transverse expansion coefficient in the presence of absorbed water is responsible for the thermally generated strain exceeding the transverse ply failure strain (ϵ_{tu}) above $T_{crit(wet)}$. A lower ϵ_{tu} for hydrothermally conditioned laminates complicates the mechanism and indicates that hydrolysis of the interface may also occur.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the service life of a military aircraft certain areas may be subjected to rapid high temperature excursions. Situations which can give rise to these "thermal spikes" include kinetic heating during supersonic flight, ground reflected efflux from the engines of VTOL aircraft and hot gases from missile efflux. Such thermal spikes have been found to influence the moisture absorption behaviour of polymer matrix composite components and, in components containing significant levels of moisture, cracking and/or delamination have been observed¹⁻². In this paper the thermal spiking behaviour of the bismaleimide modified epoxy carbon fibre composite system, Narmco Rigidite 5245C, is reported.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Crossply (0₄°/90₄°/0₄°) laminates of Rigidite 5245C were prepared using the manufacturers' recommended standard autoclave cure cycle of 2 hours at 177°C. 40 x 40 mm specimens, cut from these laminates, were given the recommended standard

post-cure of 4 hours at 210°C before being dried to constant weight for testing.

Two thermal spiking regimes, one above and one below the glass transition region, were adopted. In both cases the heating and cooling rates were 15K min⁻¹, with a 5 min hold at the peak spike temperature. The peak temperatures selected were 100°C and 250°C. Half of the specimens were hygrothermally conditioned in a relative humidity of 96%RH at a temperature of 50°C, for a period of 3 days prior to spiking, while the other half were retained in the dry state. Specimens were thermally spiked at intervals of 2 days, 2 days then 3 days, and were returned to their hygrothermal environment between spikes. They were weighed before and after each thermal spike, as were the control specimens.

To identify the minimum thermal spiking temperature necessary to induce cracking of the material an iterative approach was adopted. An identical thermal spiking programme to that described above was employed, with the exception that the peak temperature was varied. Penetrant enhanced X-radiography was used to indicate the presence of cracks generated during thermal spiking.

Measurements of the mechanical properties of both dry and hygrothermally conditioned Rigidite 5245C were made, to assist in the evaluation of the thermal spiking data, with acoustic emission being used to identify the first transverse cracking strain of crossply laminates. The thermal expansion coefficients of both dry and hygrothermally conditioned material were measured by TMA, and this gave a further insight into possible damage mechanisms. The effect of absorbed moisture on the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the material was also examined using DMTA. The mechanical properties, and the TMA and DMTA measurements, were only carried out on dry specimens or those which had reached their equilibrium moisture contents (M_∞) in 96% RH at 50°C.

3. RESULTS

Thermal spiking of the hygrothermally conditioned Rigidite 5245C to 100°C resulted in enhanced moisture uptake (Fig 1). No cracks could be observed by penetrant enhanced X-radiography.

However, thermal spiking of the hygrothermally conditioned material to 250°C resulted in a significant weight loss, which increased with increasing numbers of thermal spikes (Fig 2). This was accompanied by severe cracking of the laminate, together with some delamination. No such effect was found to occur in the dry material although a small loss of weight was observed (Fig 3).

An iterative approach was adopted to identify the temperature at which cracking of the hygrothermally conditioned material occurred. It was significant that the level of induced damage increased with thermal spike temperature. A series of 175°C thermal spikes resulted in the appearance of a number of cracks in the 90° ply of the crossply specimens (Fig 4(a)), while a spike temperature of 185°C resulted in transverse cracking of both the 0° and 90° plies (Fig 4(b)). Raising the thermal spike temperature to 200°C lead to a further increase in the number of

Fig 1: Moisture absorption curve for Rigidite 5245C $0_4/90_4/0_4$ crossply laminate exposed to a hygrothermal environment of 96% RH at 50°C and subjected to a thermal spike of 100°C.

Fig 2: Moisture absorption curve for Rigidite 5245C $0_4/90_4/0_4$ crossply laminate exposed to a hygrothermal environment of 96% RH at 50°C and subjected to a thermal spike of 250°C.

Fig 3: Weight loss curve for Rigidite 5245C $0_4^\circ/90_4^\circ/0_4^\circ$ crossply laminates stored under vacuum and subjected to a thermal spike of 250°C .

Fig 4: X-radiographs of Rigidite 5245C $0_4^\circ/90_4^\circ/0_4^\circ$ crossply laminates exposed to a hydrothermal environment of 96% RH at 50°C after thermal spiking to (a) 175°C , (b) 185°C and (c) 200°C .

cracks generated in the material (Fig 4(c)).

The results of the tensile tests performed on both dry and hygrothermally conditioned unidirectional Rigidite 5245C are collected in Table 1. It can be seen that hygrothermal conditioning causes a decrease in transverse modulus (E_t), transverse failure strain (ϵ_{tu}) and transverse strength (σ_{tu}). Furthermore, as shown by DMTA, hygrothermal conditioning causes a decrease in the matrix glass temperature, T_g from 210°C in the dry state to 177°C at a M_w of 0.48%.

TABLE 1

Comparison of the transverse tensile properties of dry and hygrothermally conditioned unidirectional Rigidite 5245C

SPECIMEN TYPE	Average				Maximum			
	M_w %	E_t GPa	ϵ_{tu} %	σ_{tu} MPa	M_w %	E_t GPa	ϵ_{tu} %	σ_{tu} MPa
0° (dry)	-	10.2	0.59	59.8	-	10.4	0.71	71.3
0° (96% RH)	0.56	10.0	0.44	45.4	0.57	10.3	0.54	56.2

TABLE 2

The transverse ply failure strain ϵ_{tu} of dry crossply laminates from Rigidite 5245C.

SPECIMEN	E_c	$\epsilon_{t1u/z}$	$\epsilon^{th/z}$	$\epsilon_{tu/z}$
0 ₂ /90 ₈ /0 ₂	64.7	0.31	0.41	0.72
0 ₄ /90 ₄ /0 ₄	120	0.25	0.44	0.69

4. DISCUSSION

Hygrothermal conditioning of 0₄/90₄/0₄° crossply laminates resulted in the formation of transverse cracks after subjection to a series of thermal spikes, to 250°C. However, no cracking was found to occur in the material thermally spiked to 100°C. Audible cracking was heard up to several minutes after specimens were removed from the thermal spiking chamber, strongly indicating that the damage occurred during the cooling of the specimens from the spike-temperature.

The thermal strain ϵ^{th} (generated in the longitudinal direction of the transverse ply of the laminate on cooling from the thermal spike-temperature to T_2) is given by equation (1):

$$\epsilon^{th} = \frac{E_l (\alpha_t - \alpha_l) (T_1 - T_2)}{E_l b + E_t d} \quad (1)$$

where T_1 is the strain free temperature, E and α and the Young modulus and linear expansion coefficient respectively. The subscripts l and t refer to the

longitudinal and transverse properties. b and d are 0° and semi 90° ply thicknesses.

As the longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient of a unidirectional ply (α_l) is effectively zero the term $(\alpha_t - \alpha_l) (T_1 - T_2)$ can be reduced to $\alpha_t(T)\Delta T$, where $\alpha_t(T)$ is the individual value across the temperature range ΔT . This term can then be evaluated by integrating the thermal expansion curve over the necessary temperature range (i.e. ΔT) and the value of residual thermal strain (ϵ^{th}) compared to the failure strain of the transverse ply.

As shown in Tables 1 and 2, the maximum recorded failure strain for a series of 90° laminates was in good agreement with the transverse failure strain of a 90° ply in a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminate obtained by summing the transverse cracking and thermal strains. The temperature dependence of the transverse thermal expansion coefficients [$\alpha_t(T)$] of the wet and dry material is presented in Fig 5. Fig 5 also demonstrates how transverse cracking can occur in some cases and not others. The lower trace corresponds to the dry material while the upper one to the hygrothermally conditioned material. Of crucial importance is the change in shape of the $\alpha_t(T)/T$ curves for the wet and dry 90° composites. The development of relaxation processes below the glass transition has been observed before and can have a profound effect on the level of thermal strain (3). For transverse cracking to occur in the dry material the area under the thermal expansion curve ($\alpha_t\Delta T$) must exceed that necessary to generate sufficient thermal strain to exceed ϵ_{tu} and induce cracking. Therefore a critical temperature ($T_{crit(dry)}$) can be defined which on cooling to ambient (RT) would make ϵ^{th} greater than ϵ_{tu} . For the dry laminate $T_{crit(dry)}$ is in excess of the glass transition temperature of the dry material ($T_{g(dry)}$), above which no thermal strain is generated in the material, and so in this case $\alpha_t\Delta T$ cannot reach the value necessary for cracking. It should be remembered that the true strain free temperature (T_1) may occur at or below T_g (defined as the maximum in $\text{Tan}\delta$).

Hygrothermal conditioning produces a sharp increase in α_t , and so the required value of $\alpha_t\Delta T$ is reached on cooling from a much lower temperature ($T_{crit(wet)}$). This temperature is below the glass transition of the hygrothermally conditioned material ($T_{g(wet)}$), and so cracking occurs. Both $T_{crit(wet)}$ and $T_{crit(dry)}$ vary with ambient temperature (RT). Therefore, cooling to lower temperatures, from a temperature previously below T_{crit} , may result in cracking although it should be noted that $\alpha_t(T)$ is much less temperature sensitive below room temperature.

The above analysis enabled the residual thermal strains generated in the plies of the hygrothermally conditioned $0_4^\circ/90_4^\circ/0_4^\circ$ laminates to be calculated in order to identify the thermal spiking temperature at which cracks would be expected. A thermal spike temperature of 175°C was found to result in cracks being formed in the 90° ply of the laminate. The residual thermal strain generated in this ply from such a spike is, at 0.72%, in excess of the transverse failure strain of

both the dry and hygrothermally conditioned material ($\epsilon_{tu} = 0.70\%$ and 0.54% respectively).

The above analysis also predicted that the thermal spiking of dry Rigidite 5245C to 250°C would result in a residual thermal strain sufficient to cause cracking in crossply laminates. This was not observed since this temperature is higher than the glass transition (and hence strain-free) temperature of the dry material. Thus the residual thermal strain cannot be simply calculated from the maximum thermal spike temperature. If the same analysis is performed by equating the glass transition temperature (as determined from $\text{Tan}\delta$ (max) from DMTA) to T_1 , a value of 0.67% was obtained which is also less than the dry transverse failure strain of 0.70% . At the true strain free temperature a lower thermal strain could be induced. Therefore, for cracking to result from thermal spiking, the critical temperature for transverse cracking (T_{crit}) must be below the glass transition or T_1 which ever is lowest. When the glass transition temperature is below this critical temperature insufficient residual thermal strain can be generated.

The enhanced moisture effect (Fig 1) as a result of thermal cycling below $T_{\text{crit(wet)}}$ is clearly related to the mechanism of expansion coefficient enhancement which must result from the thermodynamic equilibration of the water molecules. Further work is in progress to elucidate this phenomenon.

Fig 5: Temperature dependence of the thermal expansion coefficients for dry Rigidite 5245C (lower trace) and after exposure to a hygrothermal environment of 96% RH at 50°C (upper trace). (Where RT is ambient temperature, T_g is the glass transition temperature and T_{crit} is the temperature necessary to cause transverse cracking).

The reduction in weight (Fig 2) associated with crack formation during thermal spiking above $T_{\text{crit(wet)}}$ is not fully understood but may reflect hydrolytic degradation at these high temperatures. This aspect is also currently being explored further.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of thermal spiking on hygrothermally conditioned Rigidite 5245C crossply laminates may take one of two forms. If the laminate is thermally spiked to a temperature below that necessary to cause cracking an increase in the equilibrium moisture content is observed. However, if the laminate is thermally spiked to temperatures in excess of this critical temperature, gross damage, in the form of cracking and delamination is accompanied by a significant weight loss.

The factors which determine whether a laminate will crack as a result of thermal spiking are: the maximum temperature, the thermal expansion coefficient, the glass transition temperature or the related strain-free temperature, and transverse failure strain of the material. All of these, with the exception of the thermal spike temperature, are determined by the relative humidity of the environment and the kinetics of the diffusion process. For this system the presence of moisture results in an enhanced thermal expansion coefficient, a depressed glass transition temperature and a reduction in transverse failure strain probably as a result of the degradation of the fibre/matrix interface. As thermal strain can only be generated below the strain free temperature, for cracking to occur, the enhancement of the matrix thermal expansion coefficient in the presence of moisture must be sufficient to more than compensate for the reduction in residual thermal strain expected from a reduction in T_1 or T_g (see equation 1). If the thermally generated strain exceeds the transverse failure strain of the hygrothermally conditioned material cracking will occur. A critical thermal spiking temperature exists, T_{crit} , which determines the probability of damage formation. For crack formation T_{crit} is below T_1 , the strain-free temperature. Since the relationship between T_1 and the matrix T_g is likely to differ in the presence of differing concentrations of moisture, to a first approximation $T_{g(\text{wet})}$ can be used to assess the likelihood of crack formation.

For the dry Rigidite 5245C crossply laminates, T_{crit} is in excess of T_g and thermal spiking does not lead to cracking.

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REFERENCES

1. T.A. Collings and D.L. Mead, "The Effect of Simulated Aircraft Engine Efflux on Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composites", RAE Technical Memorandum Mat/Str 1082 (1986).
2. T.A. Collings and D.E.W. Stone, Composite Structures, 3, 341 (1985).
3. F.R. Jones, M.J. Mulheron and J.E. Bailey, J.Mater.Sci. 18, (1983) 1522 and 1533.